

Improvement Efforts Indonesian Language Literacy

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ABSTRACT

The Literacy Movement is a participatory activity involving all school members (learners, teachers, principals, education personnel, school supervisors, school committees, and parents) This is related to the learning carried out in schools that Literacy is synonymous with reading and writing activities including how a person communicates in society. Literacy also means social practices and relationships related to knowledge, language and culture (UNESCO, 2003). Students' abilities as learning subjects in the School. Literacy Movement include the ability to determine, identify, find, evaluate, create information in an organized manner in order to communicate it to each individual to actively participate in learning at school and in society. Currently, the meaning of literacy has developed, which includes various fields of knowledge used. There are several components of literacy (Suragangga, 2017), namely early literacy, basic, library, media, technology, and visual. Early literacy is a listening competency by understanding the use of spoken language in the environment Basic literacy includes Indonesian language competencies (listening, reading, speaking and writing), counting, and critical thinking.

INTRODUCTION

Literacy in Indonesian needs to be instilled by paying attention to listening, reading, speaking, and writing skills in order to be skillful in language. The meaning of literacy has developed so that it requires students to practice critical thinking with The purpose of this study was to improve literacy skills in Indonesian. The problem studied in the research is to examine students' interest in reading and difficulties in understanding the contents of the book. The research used a qualitative descriptive method, namely describing the results of strengthening Indonesian language literacy. The results showed that strengthening Indonesian language literacy was able to improve language literacy in terms of students' interest in reading and critical understanding.

Improving student literacy is no easy task, but by following some of the tips above, parents and educators can help students develop better reading, writing and speaking skills. This will help students to reach their academic potential and succeed in the future.

Indonesian language learning in schools is not about the science of language or literature but rather improving the ability to communicate orally and in writing. Thus, Indonesian language learning in schools today must be directed at efforts to increase literacy culture.

Literacy according to the old definition leads to the ability to read and write (Kern 2000: 3) However, in its development literacy not only involves the ability to read and write, but also other language activities, namely speaking and listening. When speaking, a person practices his verbal skills orally by utilizing logic to show his understanding, as well as when listening to a spoken text, a person uses all his language competencies to understand the meaning conveyed by the source of the sound.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Listening and reading skills are categorized as receptive language skills, while speaking and writing skills are categorized as productive language skills. Receptive skills are abilities related to passive actions, while productive abilities are active actions. The four skills must be mastered by students in school learning. Therefore, it is necessary to have an effective and innovative learning strategy so that language learning in schools runs well. Literacy is a literate activity in reading and writing, but in its development it has become multi literacy.

Indonesian language has four aspects, namely listening, reading, speaking, writing skills which are one unit. GLS is a reading activity for 15 minutes before learning begins with a period of time every day. There are three GLS activities namely habituation, development, and learning. This movement is carried out to build 21st century skills through the implementation of a literacy culture on a regular basis. Based on research conducted, 90% of students like reading fiction and 10% of students like reading non-fiction, and students are able to master understanding the contents of the book after reading as much as 70% and 30% of students find it difficult to understand the contents of the book after reading. So if analyzed, students are able to speak Indonesian well. So, students have experienced

changes for the better in literacy culture and critical thinking in processing the information they receive.

METHODOLOGY

Methodology regarding efforts to increase Indonesian language literacy can involve several important steps. First, determining research objectives, such as increasing reading or writing literacy. A literature review to understand theories related to Indonesian language literacy. Designing experiments or developing programs, such as using technology in language learning. Fourth, collect data through surveys, tests or observations to evaluate the effectiveness of efforts to increase literacy. Fifth, data analysis to identify patterns and trends in research results. Finally, preparing a research report which includes findings, conclusions and recommendations for developing Indonesian language literacy. Improving Indonesian language literacy involves a comprehensive approach, including. Enhanced Curriculum, Develop a curriculum that focuses on language skills, reading, and comprehension. Incorporate engaging materials relevant to local culture.

Teacher Training, Provide professional development for teachers, equipping them with effective teaching methods and resources to engage students in learning. Interactive Learning, Integrate technology and interactive learning tools to make the learning process more engaging and effective. Community Involvement, Engage parents and communities in literacy programs, emphasizing the importance of reading at home and creating community libraries or reading spaces. Early Childhood Education, invest in early childhood education programs that lay the foundation for language skills, ensuring children enter school with basic language abilities. Reading Initiatives, launch reading campaigns, book fairs, and storytelling events to promote a culture of reading and make books more accessible.

Assessment and Monitoring, implement regular assessments to track students' progress, identify challenges, and provide targeted support to those struggling with literacy skills.

Public Awareness, raise awareness about the significance of literacy through media campaigns, seminars, and workshops, encouraging society to value and invest in education. Inclusive Education, Ensure that literacy programs are inclusive, catering to diverse learning needs, including students with disabilities and those from marginalized communities. Government Support, advocate for policies that support education, allocate adequate funds, and create a conducive environment for effective literacy initiatives. Continuous evaluation and adaptation of these efforts are essential to address specific challenges and make meaningful progress in Indonesian language literacy.

RESEARCH RESULT

Efforts to improve Indonesian language literacy often involve targeted research initiatives, curriculum enhancements, teacher training programs, and the promotion of reading habits. Collaborations between government, educational institutions, and non-profit organizations are key in implementing

effective strategies. Continuous assessment and adaptation of methods based on research findings are vital to ensure sustainable progress in Indonesian language literacy.

Based on the results of the analysis above, things that need to be improved are; (1) teachers are expected to be able to set a good example by being disciplined in carrying out GLS activities, (2) teachers provide adequate book facilities, (3) teachers provide creative motivation so that students are interested. When these things are able to be implemented well, the results that will be achieved will be maximized. Students become happy in literacy so that a culture of literacy is formed in themselves and bring optimal creativity to work. Reading, writing and speaking skills are essential for every individual, including students. Good literacy skills will help students in the learning process and improve their academic abilities. Therefore, improving students' literacy should be a priority in education. This should be the concern of teachers/educators as well as parents/guardians.

DISCUSSION

In relation to the definition of literacy, there are three types of literacy, namely visual literacy, oral literacy, and printed or written literacy.

1. Visual Literacy in School

Visual literacy is an individual's ability to recognize the use of lines, shapes, and colors so as to interpret actions, recognize objects, and understand symbolic messages. In general, visual literacy focuses on interpreting one's visual images which is also related to reading and writing skills. Visual literacy allows a child who has just entered school to be able to compose a visual picture of a story coherently and correctly even though he or she is not yet able to read. Through visual literacy even a young child who has not yet learned to walk will be able to organize books or various toys around him. However, of course, visual literacy is developed far beyond these initial abilities Baynham (1995) mentions four categories of visual literacy, namely

1. Comprehension of the main idea is the ability to understand a visual message.
2. Perception of part or whole relationships, i.e. the ability to identify details that support the meaning of the whole
3. Imaginary-reality discrimination, which is the ability to infer or surmise the relationship between symbols and reality. Introduction to artistic media, i.e., the ability to identify the unique properties of the media used.

In its implementation in schools, visual literacy can be done through several learning activities using various types of media. Two media for developing visual literacy include pictures and movies. Picture media intended for the early grades should vary and include photographs, picture books of famous artists' work travel posters of various types of animals fruits, plants or others. The selection of the type of picture

should be based on the fact that the picture can foster interest in reading.

2. Oral Literacy in School

Oral literacy is the ability of individuals to convey their ideas orally proficiently. In oral literacy, a person who adheres to perception will assume that the most important needs in communication are speaking and listening, while reading and writing are considered important skills, but not as primary skills needed in everyday life. In practice at school, oral literacy has a very important role in conveying the ideas of both teachers and students. Teachers sometimes need to convey ideas to explain certain theories orally. Likewise, students, to check students' understanding of certain material, teachers need to instruct students to convey it orally. For this reason, oral literacy to students needs to be trained and familiarized so that the ideas in the mind and the delivery of ideas through oral can be in line. Training and habituation of oral literacy in Indonesian language learning can be done by getting students used to discussing in front of the class to express their opinions. In the discussion process students will also experience a question and answer process that utilizes oral literacy. Students also need to be trained to invite others (persuasive) through speech activities. In addition, reciting poetry and dialoguing in drama texts can also foster oral literacy in the field of literature. For early grade students, telling stories about their experiences to tourist attractions, their activities from waking up to going back to sleep is a way to foster oral literacy.

3. Written Literacy in Schools

Literacy towards written or printed texts is described as activities and skills that relate directly to printed texts either through reading (reading) or writing (writing). In developed countries, there is an assumption that the use of print or written media is a major activity in daily life. When literacy activities are carried out, students are strongly influenced by their knowledge. To be able to decode language through reading activities requires a certain level of knowledge. Reading is not just looking at words or simply spelling out words and then translating them, but must understand what is seen and translated. Likewise with writing activities, writers must organize their ideas so that their readers can understand them. A text composed of a few simple words, using the same sentence patterns that are repeated with connotative word choices will be difficult to understand. In contrast, texts composed of varied words, using natural sentence patterns with denotative word choices will be easier to understand.

4. Learning Literacy at School

Efforts to improve literacy in schools can be carried out in various forms of activities, for example in grade two students are invited to do puzzle games, arrange letters into names on a paper, both personal names, names of favorite animals, names of objects around, and arrange word cards into sentences. Other forms of learning activities include

reading song texts while singing or listening to stories. Through story telling activities, children eventually memorize the content of the story and then read it themselves. These activities must be carried out simultaneously. As technology develops, in some schools, students have been introduced to computers, so literacy activities can be carried out through the use of computers. Students can express their ideas directly by typing on the computer. The introduction of this computer will prepare children with the technology that is developing in society. Children will not be gaptak (stuttering technology) to the cell phone internet, Wi-Fi that is developing in society because they have been introduced and trained at school. Assignments given by teachers in every lesson are a process to foster students' literacy culture. Students may feel forced when the teacher says the assignment must be completed today and collected and each student is asked to present the results in front of other students. However, a student may feel happy when he or she presents the results of the assignment in front of the class and then his or her friends say, "I like your delivery style" Both cases are examples of responses to literacy activities at school.

Here are some ways that parents or educators can try to improve student literacy:

1. Introduce the habit of reading at an early age.
A reading habit built early on will help students become more accustomed to reading and broaden their horizons. Parents and educators can provide books that are appropriate to the age and interests of students to help them build reading habits.
2. Create a conducive learning environment.
A conducive learning environment can help students focus and be comfortable in the learning process. Parents and educators can create an attractive classroom, by providing adequate learning equipment, such as books, whiteboards, and computers.
3. Using technology in learning.
Technology can help students develop their literacy. Parents and educators can use engaging software and apps to help students learn to read and write more easily and enjoyably. But like a double-edged sword, the use of technology such as the internet and software also has negative effects, apart from providing positive effects. Therefore, good supervision must still be done so that students only get positive effects from the use of this technology.
4. Encourage discussion and reflection.
Discussion and reflection can help students develop a better understanding of what they read. Parents and educators can engage students in discussions about books or articles that help them formulate their own questions about the books or articles they read, as well as help them formulate their own questions and opinions.
5. Provide feedback and support. Feedback and support from educators is essential to help students improve their literacy skills. Parents and

educators can provide constructive feedback and support students in the learning process.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Literacy is a literate activity in reading and writing, but in its development it has become multiliteracy. Indonesian language has four aspects, namely listening, reading, speaking, writing skills which are one unit. GLS is a reading activity for 15 minutes before learning begins with a period of time every day. There are three GLS activities namely habituation, development, and learning. This movement is carried out to build 21st century skills through the implementation of a literacy culture on a regular basis. Based on research conducted, 90% of students like reading fiction and 10% of students like reading non-fiction, and students are able to master understanding the contents of the book after reading as much as 70% and 30% of students find it difficult to understand the contents of the book after reading. So if analyzed, students are able to speak Indonesian well. So, students have experienced changes for the better in literacy culture and critical thinking in processing the information they receive.

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ADVANCED RESEARCH

Literacy initially only included the ability to read and write. However, in its development literacy not only involves reading and writing skills, but also other language activities, namely speaking and listening. The four abilities are students' language skills that must be mastered in language learning. Listening and reading are categorized into receptive language skills while speaking and writing are categorized into productive language skills. Literacy in students that must be developed includes visual literacy, oral literacy and literacy of printed or written text. These literacy skills are developed in various forms of literacy events with literacy processes supported by language and literacy events. The three types of literacy will be well realized in schools if teachers are able to use creative and innovative approaches that are tailored to the characteristics of students

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